

Noninvasive visualization of immune cells in the upper dermal microvasculature for diagnosis of severe inflammatory conditions V2

Version 1

Description

The purpose of the DMP is to have a protocol for organizing reflectance confocal videomicroscopy data acquired in this research project.

We plan to collect videos of immune cell motion in the topmost skin capillaries by reflectance confocal videomicroscopy of 10 healthy volunteers and 10 patients with sepsis.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Inga Saknite (0000-0002-4000-5485)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Noninvasive visualization of immune cells in the upper dermal microvasculature for diagnosis of severe inflammatory conditions V2

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Organizations:

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Contact: Saknite Inga (inga.saknite@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: ESS2024/465-PG-4 "Noninvasive visualization of immune cells in the upper dermal microvasculature for diagnosis of severe inflammatory conditions"

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Restricted

Publication Date:

Data Management Plan | Noninvasive visualization of immune cells in the upper dermal microvasculature for diagnosis of severe inflammatory conditions V2 CC-BY-4.0 DOI: -12/12/2024

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

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Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose is to collect reflectance confocal videomicroscopy data of blood cell motion in the topmost capillaries of skin of patients with sepsis and healthy volunteers.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Clinical data
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- PNG
- Others

AVI

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data exist

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers and clinicians in critical care medicine

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

Metadata might contain sensitive information

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Access will be given upon request to the author by a shareable link via e.g. SharePoint

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

ImageJ, movie player

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Inga Saknite (0000-0002-4000-5485)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- IRB protocol
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Pseudonymization

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